

Low Carbohydrate and High Fat or Keto Diet Effect on HbA1c Levels in Type 2 Diabetics

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Abstract:

Objective: To know the impact of Low carbohydrate and high fat or Keto diet effect on Hb1C levels in patients with Type 2 diabetics. Participants with type2 diabetes restrict their carbohydrate intake to 30g or less daily, increase fat, and maintain a modest but not high protein intake to induce a state referred to as “nutritional keto-sis”.

Material and Method: 130 type2 DM patient with HbA1c level $7.8\% \pm 1.3$, mean glucose level $169\text{mg/dl} \pm 31$ are made to follow Low carbohydrate and high fat diet for 3months of duration HbA1c level are estimated

Result: After 3months of follow up 15 dropouts 5 no effect remaining 110 show decrease in HbA1c level to $6.43\% \pm 1.47$ & mean glucose level $137\text{mg/dl} \pm 28$, p value < 0.0010 shows significant variation, linear regression for HbA1c $-r^2: 0.53$, glucose $r^2: 0.49$.

Conclusion: No adverse effects except mild constipation. Patients on drugs decreased usage from 3 to 1 or nil at 3months. In summary Low carbohydrate and high fat diet over 3 months led to a remarkable reduction in HbA1c levels, it lead to greater improvements in symptoms associated with type II diabetes.

Keywords: Low carbohydrate and high fat diet, HbA1c Levels, low carbohydrates.

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Introduction

For healthy life healthy diet is important, as old saying “You are what you eat”. In today world this saying as diabetes and obesity are pandemic. As for 8th edition of International Diabetes federation by 2045, 629 million people worldwide under age 20-79 will be diabetic [1]. Nutrition is key for preventing type 2 diabetes (T2D) and obesity, there is no specific data to treat and prevent these life style disorders based on which dietary practice will be best. In last few year ketogenic diets (KD) or Low carbohydrate and high fat diets (LCHF) became well known diets in scientific and general public through social media as diets for lose weights, dedicated book, discussions, recipes became top list in social media years list. These diets have effective results in losing weight, but there is evidence these diets should be followed with caution when using for longer period by young people and individuals with predisposing conditions and diseases [2, 3], LCHF diet use not only help in weight reduction but studies tells they have effect on chronic diseases particularly diabetes.[4]

Pathophysiology of Diabetes

Main hormone that regulates the uptake of glucose from the blood into most cells of the body, especially liver, adipose tissue and muscle, is Insulin except smooth muscle, in which insulin acts via the IGF-1. Deficiency of insulin or the insensitivity of its receptors plays a main role in all forms of diabetes mellitus.[5]

Body obtains glucose from three main sources intestinal absorption of food the breakdown of glycogen (glycogenolysis), the storage form of glucose found in the liver; and gluconeogenesis, glucose generation from non-carbohydrate substrates in the body.[6] Insulin plays a critical role in regulating glucose levels in the body. Insulin stimulates storage of glucose in form of glycogen in different storage organs, it inhibits the process of breakdown of glycogen in gluconeogenesis, and Insulin also helps in transport of glucose to fat and muscle cells.

Major modifiable risk factors (excess weight, unhealthy diet, physical inactivity and tobacco use) are similar in all regions around world relationship with type 2 diabetes. Growing evidence that the underlying determinants of diabetes are reflection

of the major forces driving social, economic and cultural change: globalization, urbanization, population aging, and the general health policy environment.[7]

Diagnosing of Diabetes

In patient presenting high blood sugar, a mean of three months blood sugar levels are estimated by HbA1c levels which helps in diagnosing diabetes mellitus and it also help in monitoring glycemic index of diabetic patients in long term follow up. [8] The test is limited to a three-month average because the average lifespan of a red blood cell is four months or 120 days. As the lifespan of red blood cell varies from individual to individual the estimation of HbA1C is measured for 3 months. In normal cell which ha normal levels of glucose it corresponds to normal level of glycated haemoglobin.

When the levels of glucose is increased in the cell the levels of glycated haemoglobin levels increases correspondingly. So diabetic patient there is increased level of glycated haemoglobin. Poor control of blood glucose level effect different organs causing disorders like eye- retinopathy, hear- cardiovascular disorders, kidney- nephropathy and nerves system- neuropathy. [9] Following restricted carbohydrate diet is one of best option which requires continues monitoring and follow up. Because LCHF or KD results in ketosis, these meal plans are not suitable for some patients with T2D, including women who are pregnant or lactating, people with risk for eating disorders, people with renal disease. Moreover the increased risk of diabetic ketoacidosis (DKA), patients taking SGLT-2 inhibitors should avoid very-low-carbohydrate/ ketogenic diets. [3]. In summary, carbohydrates source, in addition to the carbohydrates amount, may have relevant effects on major health outcomes in the general population. With adequate patient selection and long-term monitoring, the reduction of CHO intake is effective in improving metabolic control in

patients with T2D, with KD achieving stronger effects than LCHF. Some national dietary project study with specific key design and long term follow up study for detection of side effects and complication due to following these dietary habits is needed.

Material and Method

Patient attending op clinic with type 2 DM are been explained about the lifestyle changes in diet they should follow with booklet covering different veg and non-veg diets with calories and nutrient values are provided for they easy usage and guide for food to take and patient who are interested in following the diet with guidance of dietician are selected for this study.

OP clinic patients of 130 type2 DM patient who are having HbA1c level $7.8\% \pm 1.3$, mean glucose level $169\text{md/dl} \pm 31$ are advise to follow the LCHF diet for 3months of duration then each patient are estimated for HbA1c level, Glucose levels are tested in clinical biochemistry analyser of Ortho diagnostic model Vitro's 5.1FS machine, In this analyser HbA1C levels are estimated by immunoturbidometry method and glucose level are estimated by Glucose oxidase – peroxidase method.

Ethics:

Patient concern is taken during consultation that there data will be used for academic and research purpose, Hospital academic committee has approved to use data for academic purpose.

Result

After 3months of follow up study we had 15 patients dropouts 5 patient showed no effect to diet management remaining 110 patient show decrease in glucose level $137\text{mg/dl} \pm 28$ (Fig: 1) and HbA1c level to $6.43\% \pm 1.47$ (Fig: 2), p value < 0.0010 shows significant variation, linear regression for HbA1c $-r^2: 0.53$, glucose $r^2: 0.49$, 95% confidence intervals of HbA1c: CI: 0.867 to 1.437, glucose CI: 23.61 to 40.0.

Figure 1: Glucose

Figure 2: HbA1C

Discussion:

Very common drawback of LCHF/KD is that people are not able to continue to follow them long-term, time period of term has no universally agreed definition, but is often defined as >12 months in a research setting. There is evidence supporting that the approach which is most likely to result in lasting health improvements is whichever one the individual is able to continue following [10], so this is an important issue. By this research there are various available options to the patient for them to choose the diet according to their needs and requirements. However, the available evidence does not support the assertion that LCHF/KD are more difficult to follow than other dietary approaches. There are still practical barriers in adopting LCHF/KD diets till today, most of the food labels are designed to support low fat diet approach readily available foods in shops and eateries are labelled as low fat way of eating(ex: sandwiches, crisps, chocolate bars are most available lunch and snack options in many places)

and many people are not support they friends and family who are following LCHF/KD as they have misconception regarding safety and efficacy on the diet and its effect on health, long term complications.

Above all misconceptions it does not mean that long term maintaining of KD diet is not possible as survey in UK dieticians done says that it is achieved by picking right individual as long as they follow and receive appropriate support and monitoring [11].

To make LCHF/KD diet more acceptable the existing barriers are to be dissipate, this will help more people to adhere to this diet. Changes in food environment availability of alternative diets are been in discussion in western world for twin epidemic of obesity and Type 2 diabetes , and it is also tied with economic priorities and health issues of person whom wish to follow. So it is necessary to provide with education and support for individuals who are willing to follow the diet.

Practical advice is given through social media platform, group education and discussions. Healthcare professionals are to help them learn about the LCHF/KD diet benefits and effects individual based, and support they patient in adopting them [12, 13]

They are more concerns regarding above discussion, there are a number of other factors often raised a concerns in relation to LCHF diet. One such concern is that LCHF diet increases the risk of hypoglycaemia. Patient who are on insulin or sulphonylureas are to be more conscious of danger effect of sever hypoglycaemia otherwise mild hypoglycaemic effects are common even in non-diabetics, In beginning of LCHF diet these medications doses are to be reduced or omitted [14] So that actual risk of hypoglycaemia in individuals following a LCHF diet, as long as they have a medication review before they begin can be prevented.

LCHF/KD diet has major criticism that it has increased risk of nutrient deficiencies. Generally any dietary approach is not planned well or not prepared based on nutrient dense of food for the individual taking will face deficiencies. There is no evidence that KD diet as risk of deficiencies. In LCHF there is often concern about fibre content in particular; there are varieties of foods that can provide fibre without increasing carbohydrate content to the diet, such as vegetables, nuts, seeds and dark chocolates these are staple components recommended when individuals adopt LCHF diet, invariably nutrient dense foods such as non-starchy vegetables, eggs and oily fish. It is discussed by Zinn et al [15], who had hypothetically case studied and demonstrated LCHF need not be deplete of any important nutrients.

Recommendations

- LCHF should be one of the options that are offered, and the possible benefits should be made clear. This include that existing evidence suggests that LCHF diet are effective as other approaches for the management of many key health markers, and they mostly have best effect in reducing the need of medication in diabetic patients.
- To support adherence to the diet, patients are able to make informed choices, patients should receive appropriate and on-going education and support.
- Concerns around the long-term impact of LCHF, and patient ability to adhere to diet, should not be used to discourage people from adopting such approaches as they are not supported by the available evidence. Patients are always informed about key health markers which should be tracked and allow to consider

of the impact of the specific changes made by the individual.

- Where relevant, patients should have a medication review before they begin restricting carbohydrate intake, and relevant health markers should be tracked carefully.
- Individuals with more complex needs, such as the presence of comorbidities and/or with special dietary requirements, should receive additional support from appropriately qualified healthcare professionals when making changes to their diet and lifestyle.

Conclusion

Patients who are involved in this study didn't have any side effect except for mild constipation. The number of patients on drugs decreased from 3 at baseline to 1 or nil at 3months. Insulin therapy or inpatient admission is not required in any of the subjects. In summary, the 5-10%-carbohydrate and high fat diet over 3 months led to a remarkable reduction in HbA1c levels, improvement in symptoms associated with type2 diabetics is seen. LCHF should therefore be promoted as a possible option for the management of Type 2 diabetes, and where patients make an informed choice to adopt a LCHF diet they are to be supported by continues monitoring by health care guidance's to achieve there targeted goals.

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